

HISTORICAL FIGURES IN THE WORKS OF NAVOI

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Annotation: the transformation of historical reality into artistic reality is considered one of the priorities in literature. Works written on a historical theme Give us spiritual and moral lessons, the socio-philosophical content in them, as well as animating the realities of a distant mosius before our eyes. This article describes the image of historical figures presented in the works of our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi.

Keywords: work, artistic texture, historical personality. history, spirituality, culture, literature, truth, ethics

The famous philosopher Arthur Schopenhauer believes that "if you want to get an overview of a period of history, let your fiction of that time be read". Because if we say that literature stands above history and more truthfully, if necessary, with certain issues and certain aspects, we will not be mistaken. An example of this is the life and work of many Haql oğzaki's works and historical figures, as well as the works attributed to them. Nowadays, we are acting as a great ground and foundation for young people to grow and mature even more.

Of course, the idea that a comparison with history is not full is also born mukin, but history can change political, which can be renewed depending on social situations and arrangements. And literature does not change, because literature is created by the people, literature is created by individuals. The concreteness of literature in many ways provides more accurate data than history. Because, having fully manifested history and the heroes of the work in literature, adibar was closely associated with that time, and even some writers themselves lived and created, and in many of his works he always embodied the noble intentions and sorrows of the people, left down in history or with woven images.

Among them, one of his historical works, written in honor of the history attributed to the pen of hazrat Alisher Navoi, is the work "history of muluki Ajam", written in comparison with the problems of history, Kings, which from their origins have a commendable and hateful character, which is a literary resource that is valuable for its philosophical-moral, socio-political, educational-ideological, These works are not only a beautiful example of our prose, but also a sort of national-spiritual values, which are considered the main content and core of the idea of building a free democratic society, which is being built today and has become our main goal. The Navoi says that the king and his Emir-officials can be of two types: "good" (righteous, orif) and "evil" (cruel, ignorant). The just and the orif praised the Kings and the Emir-officials, or rather, the ones he dreamed of. "Kofiri odil ani obod etib, Mo'mini zolim ani barbod etib".

An example of this is the reference to Shopur in the work. This is how the Sultan of the word Estate describes Shopur's origin and life path, relying on historical foundations. Shopur is the son of King Ardashir of Iran from the Sassanids. He continued to expand and strengthen

the territory of the state, which began under his father. He conquered large territories. Near Edessa, tormor brought Roman troops and captured Emperor Valerian as well as a large part of his army. Subjugated Syria, Armenia, Mesopotamia.

Shopur also took over the provinces of Herot, Gircania, Kushan city and others against the Kushan Kingdom by making raiding campaigns into Turan territory. His upbringing as a wise and righteous king is revealed as early as the age of six. The minister of shopur, Shahrđi, one day conveys the sad news to him, there is a big bridge from which the people are benefiting, and he conveys that the bridge has become a ruin and the people are left on the other bank of Dayo. The young king ordered another bridge to Penny, and the bridge was built, and the people began to use it in a pleasant pastime. But Shopur's time coincided with the Arab conquest, which soon after this event was invaded by the Arabs and remains in the hands of his aunt. Burned in a coming-of-age revenge, Shopur helps the arab Queen to take the castle and takes the castle.

On the same night, on the path of hatred towards the Arabs, he does not spare the Queen, but tortures her with torture. After that, Shopur zul began to be called aktof, and his executions and repression of Muslims continued. During this period, Molik binni Nasrkim, the ancestor of the Prophet Muhammad sallallohu alayhi vasallam, was the king of the Arabs and was in the same period as Shopur, and asked him the reason for this tyranny and dishonesty. Then he replied, "Say Shopur-tikim, horoscopes report to the manga, Muhammad said," the prophet of the cavalry, sallalolhu alayhi vasallam, this people appeared, took the throne from my generation and finished the alar, so I would like to prevent this. Molik ayti: first of all, the Holy astrologers will be truthful, if the words of the second great and the last destiny are true, you are better not to make this Bedouin this people, and if the Noble state appears, if it is your desire to do this AF'olingdin', then the generation of the most fragile defect is mature. This so-called Shopur ul left the job. Thankfully lilolamine. So this owner is in the state honor, about a thousand years ago his own valodatidine will save the nosy oppressors. The name of Humayun is said to be bila soyir nos ölümdin and the king will be freed by sinless ölümakdin and shaqovatdin, SallAllahu Alai and alo olihi and naslihi and ashobihi and sallam'. From this conversation we can know that no matter how oppressive the opinion of a fortuneteller with a just perception is not his own decision and, not yet coming into the world, he confessed to the well-being of his ancestors and descendants and the fact that Muslims became leaders and brought good deeds to the peoples, and regretted what he did

The work of Alisher Navoi began to be studied from its time and has not lost its value for the past V century. This is due to the uniqueness of Navoi's work, serjeanty and the words in the verses are not only in harmony with each other, rhyming, but also in the fact that history reflects the essence of the true realities in different ways, depending on the scales of the mind of its student.

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